

Studies on N-substituted 3 : 5-Dihalo Propesin Derivatives as Potential Local Anesthetics

(Miss) J. N. ACHARYA and K. A. THAKER

University Department, of Chemistry Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar-364002.

Manuscript received 13 July 1976, revised 17 August 1977, accepted 24 November 1977

Potential local anesthetics of the type :

where X is Br or I and R is from different amines, have been prepared. The free bases have been converted into their hydrochlorides and some of them have been tested for their local anesthetic activity.

ESTERS of *p*-aminobenzoic acid are known for their local anesthetic activity¹. It has been reported that local anesthetic activity increases with increasing the number of carbon atoms of ester group and is highest in Butyl *p*-aminobenzoate².

In continuation of our previous work³, we have prepared N-substituted 3 : 5-dibromo/diiodo propesin derivatives of the type,

where X is Br or I and R is alkyl, aryl, heterocyclic or alicyclic amino moiety. The compounds have been prepared by chloroacetylation of 3, 5-dibromo propesin or 3, 5-diiodo propesin and then condensation with various amines.

The free bases are converted into their hydrochlorides by passing dry HCl gas in the ethereal solution. Some of them have been investigated for their local anesthetic activity. They have been tested for surface anesthesia by corneal block method of Chance and Lobstein⁴ and for intradermal anesthesia following the method of Parel⁵ on guinea-pig. The activity was compared with cocaine, HCl, procaine, HCl and lignocaine, HCl. The results recorded in Table 2 indicate that the compounds show better intradermal anesthetic activity rather than surface anesthetic activity. Preliminary studies prove that they are better than procaine because they have activity equal to that of procaine with longer duration of local anesthetic action. In surface anesthesia, two out of three have activity equal to that of lignocaine with almost equal duration of action.

IR Spectra :

The IR spectra have been recorded on Beckmann IR-5 spectrophotometer at the Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar in nujol as mulling agent. Bands are observed as follows for 3, 5-dibromo propesin at (approx.) 3450, 3400, 3100, 2915, 2870, 1730, 1685, 1600, 1555, 1500, 1460, 1380, 1315, 1290, 1245 and, 890 cm^{-1} .

For 3, 5-diiodo propesin at (approx.) 3450, 3400, 3140, 2910, 2875, 1730, 1675, 1600, 1560, 1520, 1460, 1380, 1310, 1275, 1240 and 895 cm^{-1} .

For N-chloroacetyl-3, 5-diiodo propesin at (approx.) 3175, 2920, 2868, 1730, 1670, 1565, 1515, 1460, 1382, 1320, 1280, 1245, 890 and 758 cm^{-1} .

For N-chloroacetyl-3, 5-dibromo propesin at (approx.) 3205, 2918, 2865, 1725, 1680, 1562, 1510, 1465, 1385, 1315, 1280, 1242, 885 and 760 cm^{-1} .

For N-morpholinoacetyl-3, 5-dibromopropesin at (approx.) 2915, 2870, 1930, 1675, 1555, 1460, 1380, 1315, 1290, 1260, 1240, 1115, 1020, 980, 865, 762 and 735 cm^{-1} .

For N-benzylaminoacetyl-3, 5-dibromo propesin at (approx.) 3310, 3245, 2925, 2875, 1730, 1690, 1520, 1460, 1380, 1560, 1515, 1275, 1245, 1195, 1140, 1125, 975, 760, 740 and 700 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Preparation of 3, 5-dibromo propesin :

Propesin (0.1 M) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and bromine (0.25 M) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring at 0°. The product separated immediately which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol in long needles, m. p. 84° (62-4.4° is reported by Wells⁶).

TABLE-1

Sl. No. (1)	R (2)	X (3)	Molecular Formula (4)	m.p. °C (5)	Requd. (6)	% N Found (6)	Requd. (7)	% Br Found (7)
1	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₉ NH	Br	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	* 84 200	6.22	6.36	41.02	41.06
2	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH	Br	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	125	5.79	5.91	33.06	33.19
3	C ₄ H ₉ NO	Br	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	99	6.03	6.09	34.48	34.10
4	C ₅ H ₁₀ N	Br	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	*213 101 *178	6.06	6.21	34.63	34.73
5	2-ClC ₆ H ₄ NH	Br	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	193	5.55	5.72	32.21	31.97
6	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ NH	Br	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	157	5.79	5.63	33.06	33.23
7	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ NH	Br	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	116	5.79	5.82	33.06	33.21
8	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ NH	Br	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	185(d)	5.60	5.91	31.99	32.09
9	2-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ NH	Br	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	162(d)	5.45	5.64	31.13	32.82
10	3-HO-C ₆ H ₄ NH	Br	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	120	5.76	5.87	32.93	33.23
11	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ NH	I	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	107	5.15	5.40	46.69	47.00
12	C ₄ H ₉ NO	I	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	220	5.02	5.24	45.52	45.91
13	C ₅ H ₁₀ N	I	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	135	5.04	4.99	45.67	45.54
14	(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ N	I	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	...	5.15	5.31	46.69	46.82
15	(C ₂ H ₁₁) ₂ N	I	C ₂₂ H ₄₄ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	...	7.49	7.63	40.43	40.25
16	C ₆ H ₁₁ NH	I	C ₁₀ H ₂₄ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	*179 *189(d)	4.91	5.06	44.55	44.65
17	C ₆ H ₅ NH	I	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	...	4.96	5.11	45.03	45.16
18	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ NH	I	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ I ₂ N ₂ O ₂	180 187:	4.96 5.69	5.11 5.82	45.03 43.94	45.16 44.08

* Hydrochlorides.

TABLE-2

(A) Surface anesthesia

Sl. No.	R	Drug conc. in %age (approx.)	%age anesthesia	Duration in minutes	Potency compared to cocaine	Potency compared to lignocaine
1.	morpholino	0.2	90.00	15.00	1/2	equal
2.	piperidino	0.4	100.00	22.00	1/2	1/2
3.	<i>n</i> -butylamino	0.2	90.00	15.50	1/2	equal
4.	cocaine	0.1	96.66	21.00
	lignocaine	0.2	100.00	14.83

(B) Intradermal Anesthesia

Sl. No.	R	Drug conc. in %age (approx.)	% age anesthesia	Duration in minutes	Potency compared procaine	Potency compared to lignocaine
1.	morpholino	0.4	97.00	65.00	equal	1/2
2.	piperidino	0.4	98.00	75.00	equal	1/2
3.	<i>n</i> -butylamino	0.4	95.00	72.00	equal	1/2
	procaine	0.4	100.00	55.83
	lignocaine	0.2	98.33	44.83

Found : N, 3.99% ; Br, 48.08% ;
 $C_{10}H_{11}Br_2NO_2$ required : N, 4.16% ; Br, 48.05%.

Preparation of 3, 5-diiodo propesin :

Propesin (0.1 M) was dissolved in aq. HCl (50%, 300 ml) and iodine monochloride in aq. HCl (12.5%, 300 ml) was added with stirring until no more precipitates were obtained. The contents were diluted with excess of water and stirring was continued for some time. The product separated as light brown precipitates which was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 113°.

Found : N, 3.30% ; I, 58.82%
 $C_{10}H_{11}I_2NO_2$ required : N, 3.25% ; I, 58.92%;

Chloroacetylation of dihalo propesin :

3,5-Dibromo/diiodo propesin (0.05M) in dry, thiophene free benzene (50 ml) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.12M) in dry, thiophene free benzene (50 ml) were refluxed on a water-bath for 3-4 hours. Benzene was distilled off to obtain the product which was washed with aq. $NaHCO_3$ (4%) and water, filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol.

N-Chloroacetyl-3,5-dibromo propesin, m.p. 182°.

Found : N 3.51% ; Br, 39.00% ;

$C_{12}H_{12}ClBr_2NO_2$ required : N 3.38% ; Br, 38.78%.

N-Chloroacetyl-3,5-diiodo propesin, m.p. 186°.

Found : N, 2.89% ; I, 50.10% ;

$C_{12}H_{12}ClI_2NO_2$ required : N, 2.75% ; I, 49.99%.

Preparation of N-substituted-3,5-dibromo/diiodo propesin derivatives :

N-Chloroacetyl-3,5-dibromo/diiodo propesin (0.05M) in absolute ethanol (15 ml) and the amine (0.12M) in absolute ethanol (15 ml) were refluxed on a water-bath for 7-9 hrs. The contents were cooled and poured on to ice-water. The product was filtered, washed with dil. HCl (4%) and water, crystallised from ethanol.

The physical and analytical data of these compounds are listed in Table 1.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank Saurashtra University for providing research facilities and C.S.I.R. for J.R.F. to one of them (J.N.A.) and to Chemistry Department, S. P. University, Vallabhvidyanagar for I.R.

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